

Intelligent Optimisation for Enhanced Ship Design

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Abstract. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) tools are revolutionising the field of ship design. These technologies not only accelerate the design process but enhance what can be explored and understood, enabling improved decision-making and improving platform performance. By allowing hundreds of options to be considered and calculated, there can be greater confidence the right design decisions are being made for the specific platform, balancing capability against cost and other considerations. Although these tools seem futuristic, they are already providing practical solutions to specific problems today. This paper explores the need for and benefits of intelligent deployment of AI-based optimisation techniques in ship design and provides a case study of what can be achieved today. Firstly, it examines the rationale for change by considering current methods used in ship design, as well as the necessity and potential benefits of AI-based optimisation methods. It considers both the design process and the overall platform design outcomes. It also discusses how integrating emerging optimisation techniques might challenge current and historic practices both now and in the future, using examples of the broader application of AI within engineering. Finally, it presents a case study on the use of ML in hull form optimisation, illustrating how this readily available technique can be effectively used in ship design projects to enhance platform capability and improve the efficiency of the design process. While AI-based optimisation tools can analyse options and collate information efficiently, the complex nature of the trade-off decisions in ship design necessitates careful human judgement. These tools therefore serve as valuable aids for experienced engineers in addressing challenges within the design space. Therefore, the role of AI and ML in ship design is one of collaboration and enhancement, rather than replacement.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Hull Form Optimisation, Parametric Modelling*

1 Background: The Case for Change

The maritime industry is undergoing a transformative shift with the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into many aspects of vessel design, maintenance and operation. AI technologies, including Machine Learning (ML), predictive analytics, and generative AI, offer the potential to enhance design efficiency, optimise performance, and improve safety. The goal is not to replace human expertise but to augment it, enabling technical experts to make more informed decisions and explore a broader design space. Exploiting potential improvements through the deployment of AI methods allows a larger design space to be explored. This enables the exploration of diverse and innovative solutions, challenging existing constraints, and offering enhanced capabilities in an efficient manner.

The ship design process is often described as a converging design spiral, involving multiple iterations where the design is reviewed, refined and matured based on previous iterations, with additional details incorporated at each stage. This illustration highlights how the design of complex platforms, such as naval and auxiliary vessels, can be a cumbersome process. Therefore, approaches which increase confidence early on in the design process or improve the efficiency of design activities can yield significant benefits.

At present, ship design processes use multiple toolsets for differing analysis areas with manual interaction needed to ensure consistency between tools. This leads to both lags in updates across disciplines and potential inconsistencies in the information used, while also increasing the risk for errors to be made. Optimisation tools have the capability to integrate inputs from multiple sources, allowing for the consideration of a wider range of parameters and their overall impact on the platform. With experienced ship designers controlling the inputs and boundaries of these studies and interpreting results, the process can be streamlined and the risk of errors reduced. Integrating a toolset in this manner within a well-defined process allows for a broader understanding of design impacts promptly. This allows risks to be identified and mitigated earlier in the design process, ensuring decisions are made based on the best possible information.

The status quo for ship design has several areas for improvement:

- **Efficiency in the Design Process:** Military ship procurement programmes span many years, from requirement definition through the various design stages, to manufacture and delivery. Efficiencies which shorten the timescales between requirement setting and delivery increase the agility of the procurement process and improve the ability to deliver the required capabilities promptly, ensuring ships entering service incorporate the latest technologies.
- **Optimisation in Ship Design:** There is an ongoing need to optimise designs to best meet customer requirements. This need is partly driven by requirements which incentivise designers to develop optimised solutions, necessitating methods to achieve these optimisations. Enhancing capability in the ship design process can include designing for energy efficiency, optimising the design around specific operations and developing more efficient arrangements. Current manual design processes primarily depend on individual experience for optimisation, which can limit the ability to quantify these optimisations. Additionally, balancing competing requirements can make it difficult to identify the best compromise of design features.
- **Minimise Repetitive Work:** Repetitive tasks stem from an iterative design process, manual optimisation approaches, and toolsets which require manual data transfer. These practices have several disadvantages, including the risk of errors, increased cost and underutilisation of team members' skills. Many of these tasks could be automated without compromising the result allowing engineers to dedicate their time to value adding activities rather than the repeated manipulation of data.
- **Bias Towards Previous Designs:** Current processes often rely on requirements derived from previous ships and lessons learnt from earlier platforms during the early design stages. While this approach can result in faster, or more numerous, design iterations, as demonstrated by the rapid, incremental evolution of Royal Navy destroyer design as part of the War Emergency Program during the Second World War, it can stifle innovative approaches to meeting customer requirements. This comes about through the inherent heritage of the data in use, automatically aligning to previous designs and bounding the perceived solution space.

Intelligent deployment of AI techniques offers benefits across these areas. This is particularly relevant to naval ship design due to the added complexity of naval ships, and the trend of procurement programmes acquiring fewer platforms with wide ranging requirements. This necessitates starting from scratch for each project, placing a greater emphasis on getting the design 'right first time'. However, there are valuable lessons which can be learnt from commercial ship design, and benefits to commercial ship design through the incorporation of AI.

2 What Does Change Look Like?

It is inevitable the use of AI will become more prevalent across all industries in the future, and ship design will be no exception. A key challenge will be to ensure AI is used intelligently and for the most efficient benefit to the overall goal of the task at hand. This involves leveraging AI's strengths while maintaining human input in the areas where AI struggles. AI is highly effective at integrating large volumes of existing content, excels in analysis by processing vast amounts of data to uncover patterns, trends, and insights which inform decision-making, and enhances productivity by automating routine and repetitive tasks. However, AI often struggles with tasks requiring subtle judgement and nuanced decision-making and may be less able to make novel connections or generate truly innovative ideas due to its reliance on historical data. AI may also struggle to adapt and provide useful results when desired outcomes are ambiguous or evolving.

Therefore, engineers working in the complex and bespoke ends of the maritime design sector will need to consider the extent to which AI models can benefit the overall design process. As requirements build up in a complex design, so do the interconnections between different aspects of a platform, including associated regulations and broader considerations of practicality and viability. For an AI model to perform effectively, the criteria it uses to measure success must capture these interconnectivities to avoid producing invalid solutions. Developing these criteria may take more time and effort than the initial process itself, negating the benefit seen, especially as the smaller number of bespoke naval ship design programmes reduces the transferability of these relationships between individual projects. Some of these relationships can be difficult to translate into criteria which can be quantified and are reliant on the input of experienced engineers, builders, operators, owners and maintainers, amongst others, to assess adequacy. The goal of using AI is not to replace human expertise but to augment it, enabling engineers to make more informed decisions, explore a broader solution space, and deliver innovative and capable designs more efficiently.

Outlined below are some areas where AI is already utilised in ship design. This list is not exhaustive but offers a glimpse into how AI models can enhance our capabilities, improve our designs, and increase our efficiency.

- **Hull Form Development** - ML and neural networks and deep learning can rapidly process data from many analysis sources (e.g. resistance estimates, seakeeping or manoeuvring models) to explore the solution space and generate optimised hull form variations. This capability allows designers to evaluate many design iterations, finding the most effective configurations for criteria of interest within defined constraints. An example on reducing resistance for hull forms with five varying parameters is further explored at the end of this paper.
- **General Arrangement** - AI can aid in developing general arrangements by managing the complex interdependencies and connections between compartments. The main challenge lies in converting subjective assessment criteria into a set of binary, rules-based criteria which can be used to create a loss function. Genetic algorithms can then be used to iterate and refine the design based on the required criteria.
- **Structural Design** - While AI is already well-developed and utilised in early-stage structural design tools (e.g. for evaluation of different structural configurations), significant time savings can be achieved in the later detailed design stages by assessing specific structural components of simple items, such as seats. These tools may not complete all detailed design tasks, but they can provide an initial assessment, saving time on the majority of simple items.
- **Regulation and Knowledge Management** - Robotic Process Automation (RPA) can be used to search for regulatory changes. The maritime domain has a complex map of sometimes conflicting regulatory domains, and it can be time consuming to track changes and interdependencies. Searching for regulatory changes as they are published is a simple and repetitive task, ideal for automation. This allows the more challenging 'interpretation' element to remain within the human domain, improving overall efficiency without degrading the outcome.

The future of ship design with AI tools should focus not only on isolated tasks but also on utilising outputs to continually develop models. While many applications in the ship design area have relatively small data reference sets, these could rapidly grow with the intelligent use of analytical models. An increase in available data, if managed wisely, should enhance the capability of AI models, further improving their overall effectiveness.

However, the increased quantity of analysis and data outputs AI models will provide should be treated with caution. Interrogating data can be time-consuming, and a larger volume of data may require more results to be taken at face value, potentially increasing reliance on the AI models and therefore increasing overall risk. For instance, surface ship stability is a dynamic phenomenon modelled in a quasi-static manner. The associated assumptions mean results should be interrogated to ensure a design can be considered safe, as the numerical criteria responses may not capture the full picture. Should stability analyses be used with AI models there is potential for a large increase in the number of cases which can be run to inform design decisions. With this increase, a smaller proportion of the overall assessed cases may be thoroughly examined, potentially reducing the understanding of the problem.

3 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning - Case Studies

3.1 Genetic Algorithms in Engineering Design

Genetic Algorithms (GA), considered a subclass of Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) [1][2], typically present themselves in two forms: gradient based, and non-gradient based methods. Gradient based optimisation methods identify what is believed to be the optimal solution by a pre-defined gradient of an objective function. A non-gradient based optimisation method, instead, globally searches the design space for solutions to what is believed to be the optimum for the objective function. Since gradient-based methods find a solution locally, exploration of the design space can be limited, and these methods sometimes settle at a local optimum, which may not be the true optimum [3][4]. Also, these methods tend to be affected by noise sensitivity, making them less reliable solvers for aerodynamic or hydrodynamic design problems compared to a non-gradient based technique [5]. Non-gradient based techniques, particularly within Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), are effective but require significant computational power.

There is still limited use of GAs in real-world industrial applications despite their promising results, in which their performance is often measured using engineering benchmarks. The novel implementation of an EA for optimisation of the shape of an engine intake duct under varied flow regimes [5] in order to minimise pressure distortion was conducted as part of research at Swansea University supported by Fujitsu. The study demonstrates the usability of GAs within engineering design. The GA used in this research was the Modified Cuckoo Search

(MCS) algorithm (non-gradient based) and is inspired by the aggressive reproductive behaviour of the Cuckoo bird [6][7]. The algorithm aims to mimic a ‘survival of the fittest’ approach, driving the solution towards a high fitness, which measures how well a solution addresses the problem. MCS is a non-gradient based optimisation technique, and therefore globally searches the design space.

In the study, the algorithm is used to manipulate the geometry of an engine intake duct on a supersonic flight vehicle by moving several control nodes, as selected by the user, within the design space. Figure 1 illustrates the concept of varied geometry by depicting a narrowed intake duct entrance, which minimises pressure distortion, the fitness function optimised for.

Figure 1. Pressure fields of the vehicle with an engine intake duct comparing the (a) initial geometry and (b) optimised geometry for a flight speed of Mach 1.4 [5].

Figure 2 shows an average improvement in fitness across several Mach numbers for the intake duct study.

Figure 2. Fitness increase over 100 generations, with final fitness values of distortion minimisation around -0.06 [5].

The y-axis represents Fitness (F), indicating the extent to which the pressure distortion is minimised, while the x-axis shows the number iterations the algorithm has performed. Each point on the graph is the best solution at a given iteration. The jumps show the algorithm has identified another location within the design space where the solution presents a better distortion rate than the previous solution, therefore its fitness is higher. Generally, solutions will improve in fitness over several generations. If the same optimisation is run again, the pattern of improvement may differ due to the algorithm’s partially random search process.

An example such as this shows the extent to which this form of geometry manipulation could be applied, where any form of parameter manipulation can be optimised for specific goals. Such an algorithm can automate this process through systematically modifying the geometry, assessing the impact and proposing next steps based on the optimisation algorithm in use, while still involving the user in the decision making process. While the

computational time required for each iteration may be similar between a manual and automated approach, the efficiency of a purely user-driven approach is defined by the ability of the user to prosecute geometry changes and make informed decisions regarding the output data, such that the same solution as an automated approach may never be reached, or the time required to reach this point would be far larger. The time taken to set up a parameterised model and an algorithm initially, however, needs to be considered alongside the frequency with which it would be re-used.

The GA concept is highly applicable to aspects of vessel design, particularly where there is not a large pool of existing data to train a model on (as would be expected in the Machine Learning example to follow). For example, the design of a hull form may be varied in several parameters controlled by nodes. An algorithm can be used to reduce resistance by manipulating some or all of these different parameters. This could be readily applied to the example process discussed at the end of this paper.

3.2 Machine Learning in Materials Engineering

Machine Learning (ML) models in engineering have made significant progress in reducing cumbersome and time-consuming design processes and unreliable, inaccurate prediction analyses, particularly in materials engineering. An example of an improved area is determining of High-performance Concrete Compressive Strength (HPCCS), enhancing materials and civil design processes [8]-[11]. Traditionally, standard compression tests can determine the actual compressive strength of High-performance Concrete (HPC), however this is time consuming and expensive. Typically, the linear empirical formula used also introduces various regression coefficients to represent the effects of different added materials. As a result, the predictability of this empirical formula becomes unreliable as the correlation between the compressive strength of HPC and its components is nonlinear [12]. Introducing an ML algorithm to accurately predict HPCCS showcases the broader applicability of ML techniques in design. For an ML model, where there is sufficient data available to split into a pre-determined train-test split ratio, the algorithm can learn, meaning it determines the relationship between the constituents and the target values. The accuracy of such ML techniques can then be compared to assess their effectiveness for a given problem.

The particular case study [8] employs the XGBoost machine learning algorithm to predict the HPCCS. XGBoost, a gradient boosting method using decision trees, builds models sequentially by minimising prediction errors and optimising the loss function. The researchers implemented an automated feature selection and hyperparameter selection pipeline to improve the model's overall accuracy. Hyperparameter tuning used a grid search across 600 configurations, evaluated via 3-fold cross-validation, resulting in 1800 model fits to find the optimal settings. The final model was trained on 927 samples and tested on 103, with predictions compared against actual values to assess performance. To enhance interpretability, a game theory-based approach was utilised to explain the influence of each input feature on the model's predictions.

The benefits of developing a ML model can be dependent on the size of the underlying data set, complexity of the relationships and relative cost of conducting traditional tests. A single use scenario of a ML model for a simple experiment with readily predictable and consistent results may not provide the intended benefits. Whereas in the HPCCS example above, a ML model can be re-used multiple times to predict responses to complicated and expensive physical testing with non-linear relationships where a large bank of existing data already exists. The benefits of such a model grow with continued usage and the integration of further input data.

ML models can be utilised in many ship design processes, in particular where large quantities of data already exist or can be readily developed. For example, tow tank testing can be time-consuming and expensive, but for many years this was the primary method by which resistance, propulsion, seakeeping and manoeuvring data was collected. As such, a large amount of data exists which can relate hull form and environmental variables to these output parameters which could be expanded upon through more recent numerical assessments. ML techniques could be used to provide future predictions in these areas. However, this would only be viable if a large enough pool of data was accessible for the algorithm to use for training and testing, without this, the outcomes may be inaccurate or untrustworthy.

3.3 Particle Swarm Optimisation in Wind Farm Layouts

Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) algorithms, like GAs, are considered a subclass of Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) [1]. Wind Farm Layout Optimisation (WFLO) is a complex problem involving multiple conflicting objectives, such as minimising land or sea surface use and maximising energy production [13]. According to the wind report 2013 of Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC), wind energy has become the second largest renewable energy source and will account for up to 25% of total renewable energy by 2035 [14]. Veeramachaneni et al. demonstrated a multi-objective PSO algorithm, used for optimising a large-scale offshore wind farm by maximising the energy production while minimising the total investment, with consideration for

wake loss [15]. The PSO EA is inspired by the social behaviour of fish schooling and bird flocking, first proposed by Kennedy and Eberhart [16].

In the case of optimising the layout of a wind farm, the methodology begins with the development of a comprehensive mathematical model which incorporates variations in wind direction and wake effects. This model uses Levelized Production Cost (LPC) as the objective function, aiming to maximise energy yields while minimising total investment costs. The PSO algorithm is employed to determine the optimal layout of wind turbines, considering both wake effects and component costs. The algorithm iteratively adjusts the positions of the turbines within the design space to find the configuration which minimizes the LPC.

The PSO algorithm's parameters, such as particle size and iteration times, are designed to ensure efficient computation and convergence to a near-optimal solution. The results suggest the PSO algorithm effectively optimised the placement of the wind turbines, with the optimised layout significantly reducing the LPC by considering both wake effects and component costs. The simulations conducted on the FINO3 reference wind farm, with an installed capacity of 800 MW, show the optimized layout achieves a 5.9% reduction in LPC for a constant spacing layout and a 6.7% reduction for a sparse layout compared to a traditional 7D layout. The optimized layouts also result in a substantial decrease in wake losses, with the constant spacing layout reducing wake losses to 19.5% and the sparse layout to 17.7%.

Additionally, the results highlight the optimised sparse layout, while slightly more expensive in terms of cable costs and power losses, provides the best overall performance in terms of energy yields and LPC. The constant spacing layout, on the other hand, offers significant savings in sea area occupation, making it a practical choice for real-world applications. This research showed PSO is a robust method for parameter-based optimisation and could be extended to different wind conditions and capacities, as well as further design applications.

PSO lends itself well to multi-objective optimisation problems, one of which is the general arrangement of ships. The general arrangement depicts the layout of a ship and is derived from many design constraints, for example, technical specifications, capacity, structural elements, safety, overall cost, and more. An optimisation method which considers all necessary parameters can automate parts of the process, enhancing the design's efficiency. This could lead to smaller ship sizes, more efficient functionality layouts, reduced environmental impact, and immediate and long-term financial benefits. However, given the number of interdependencies and design constraints involved for a complex ship, human involvement must be retained in the process to yield viable results.

These three studies show examples of how different branches of AI have been used successfully within wider engineering design and analysis, with suggestions of how these techniques could be translated to ship design. The examples of GA, ML and PSO demonstrate how the details of the problem at hand, including available data, complexity of the relationships and the desired output require different methodologies and algorithms to solve. The following case study looks at work BMT has conducted in improving the hull form optimisation process for reducing resistance, leveraging the benefits of AI discussed earlier in this paper.

4 Case Study: Machine Learning (ML) in Hull Form Design

BMT has conducted extensive in-house research into the application of ML for hull form optimisation. The basis hull form selected for this study was the ELLIDA concept for a multi-role support and logistics ship. Initially developed using traditional manual processes, the complexity of the design made it an ideal candidate for development using parametric modelling and ML optimisation.

Three key components are essential for the successful implementation of ML in this context. Firstly, the problem needs to be described as a search through combinatorial space. Hull form design involves navigating a vast network of potential designs, so a systematic approach is required to explore numerous variables and constraints to identify optimal solutions.

Secondly, a substantial amount of data and/or a robust simulation capability is needed. Training and validating AI models requires extensive datasets. Additionally, having a robust simulation capability enables the generation of synthetic data, testing of various design scenarios, and evaluation of performance metrics under different conditions. This approach ensures models are both accurate and versatile.

Lastly, defining a clear metric or objective is crucial for guiding the optimisation process. This could involve minimising drag, maximising stability, or achieving a balance between multiple performance criteria. These metrics serve as the basis for evaluating and comparing different hull form designs, ensuring the optimisation process is aligned with our overall design goals.

By addressing these three components, BMT was able to leverage ML to enhance our hull form design process, leading to more efficient and effective optimisation outcomes. The process developed establishes relationships

between defined hull form parameters and analysis outputs, guiding subsequent assessment rounds and highlighting optimum solutions from the evaluated hull forms.

Focussing on the first component, a combination of software tools was utilised to develop a parametric model and automation process to rapidly and methodically generate a series of hull forms defining the analysis space at each round of assessment. Rhinoceros 3D (Rhino) with the Grasshopper programming environment, and Python were integral to the approach. Rhino is a versatile 3D Computer-aided Design (CAD) application widely used for design and engineering tasks. Grasshopper, a visual programming language within Rhino, enables the creation of complex parametric designs through a graphical interface. Python further extended the capabilities of Rhino and Grasshopper, enabling the automation of tasks and programmatic manipulation of the geometry.

Parametric modelling is a powerful technique in CAD which uses parameters to define and manipulate geometric models. Control points or vertices are adjusted to alter these parameters, for hull forms this could be macro variables like length or finer variables like bilge radius. In automated parametric modelling, the careful selection of parameters and iterations is essential as the total number of parametric combinations can increase exponentially, potentially resulting in an unmanageable optimisation process. To ensure the generated designs meet project requirements, constraints related to geometry and hydrostatics are applied. These constraints ensure the optimisation outcomes remain feasible and relevant.

In this study, the second component was addressed using the ShipFlow potential flow code XSPAN, enabling the rapid calculation of wave resistance for parametrically generated hull forms. XSPAN was combined with XBOUND for controllable meshing using an input script. This script followed a consistent format of variables to ensure each of the hull forms could be assessed with the minimum of human input. Similarly, the output results from XSPAN followed a consistent format to allow easy identification of the parameters of interest in the third component of each round of assessments. This study focussed on using ML for optimising hull forms based on reducing resistance, however, the same process can be used for either single output results or a combination of factors. For example, resistance could be measured over a range of speeds to allow calculation of an overall fuel usage metric, or a seakeeping assessment through a strip theory code could be readily introduced alongside the wave resistance estimates. The possibilities are wide ranging and largely depend on available computing time and the ease with which the software can be automated to evaluate numerous parametrically created hull forms.

Ansys optiSlang was used to address the third of the defined key components. This software is specifically designed for optimising parametric designs. Through utilising Robust Design Optimisation (RDO) methods, an optimal hull form can be identified from the initial analysis set, and statistics produced on which design parameters have the most significant impact on the chosen output variables and constraints placed on the design. This allows the user to determine which design parameters should be considered for further iterations, either to explore parts of the hull form further or refine the hull form based on the already considered variables and constraints. The resistance and geometric characteristics of hullforms generated and assessed in components one and two provided the dataset to train the model, with the geometric parameters acting as input variables and the response variables used for the prediction aspect. These parameters and variables are discussed below.

The three-step process is depicted in Figure 3, with each step aligning to the three ‘Automation’ aspects and linked by an overarching Python script.

Figure 3. Representation of the BMT ML Supported Parametric Assessment Process

To demonstrate the methodology, the first iteration used as a proof of concept is described as follows. Five input variables for the ELLIDA hull form (length and breadth of bulbous bow, half angle of entrance, bilge radius,

and position of the forward end of the midbody) were considered with a defined range of values, resulting in 8400 individual forms. Of these, 816 complied with the geometry and hydrostatics constraints (for displacement, longitudinal centre of buoyancy, and transverse metacentric height) and were assessed using XPAN. The output wave resistance coefficients were combined with each of the five input variables and the corresponding hydrostatic data for each valid form for analysis using optiSlang. This analysis identified, for this form and the variables considered, the bilge radius and position of the forward end of the midbody were significantly more influential than the other three variables (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Output response showing the relative influence of each input variable assessed

The impact of each variable on a non-dimensionalised resistance can also be explored (see Figure 5), with individual parameters and constraints varied to assess their resulting impact on the non-dimensionalised resistance. Along with other considerations, these assessments then guide the choice of parameters for subsequent iterations and/or further optimisation.

Figure 5. Input parameter values and corresponding output parameters and results for all 816 cases

A human touchpoint was included at the analysis stage of each iteration. While it is possible to automate the process to make decisions based on the most influential factors and continue with further iterations (a more comprehensive ML approach), using the data to suggest and inform decisions rather than automatically execute them retains more control. This approach minimises the risk of the model producing forms which may be unsuitable due to design constraints from other disciplines (e.g. mechanical engineering, structural engineering, electrical engineering, among others) and may not be easily translatable into mathematical functions.

This study also demonstrated how, once a well parameterised model has been developed, a single iteration of developing and evaluating hundreds of hull forms can indicate the relative importance of different features more quickly than manually developing, assessing and analysing a single form using traditional methods. With each repetition of this approach, more data is gathered, and its effectiveness continues to improve.

5 Conclusion

It is inevitable the use of AI will become increasingly widespread in ship design, making it crucial to identify how this can be used intelligently for maximum efficiency towards the overall goal. Many areas of the ship design process already benefit from AI tools, reducing overall timescales (increasing efficiency in the design process), providing greater opportunities for optimisation, minimising repetitive work requirements and reducing bias towards prior designs.

Different applications of AI and ML in maritime design necessitate adjusting the approach to achieve the desired outcome. A purely design based scenario (for example, iterating through a node controlled hull form geometry to reduce resistance) would require a different underlying approach to producing a standard series assessment based on large quantities of input data. This paper has given case studies across wider industry to demonstrate some of the available approaches as well as a specific example of how BMT are using automation and ML to improve the design of hull forms for reduced resistance in a more efficient manner than traditional approaches and with a greater understanding of the relationships between input parameters, output variables and constraints for particular series' of hull forms.

The aim of using AI tools is to augment, not replace, human expertise. When applied intelligently to specific challenges within the design lifecycle, AI can be highly effective. By targeting AI applications to specific areas, engineers can increase productivity and achieve better outcomes without sacrificing the essential human input on

creativity and judgment. Embracing AI's benefits will allow the maritime industry to enhance efficiency, unlock innovation, and achieve operational characteristics which were previously out of reach. The development of the ELLIDA hull form to reduce resistance with these tools is one specific example.

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